

Table 2. Yield of 4 new upland rice varieties in farmers' fields in Kambia District, Sierra Leone.

Variety	1986-87				1987-88			
	Kamaranka	Funkia	Petifu	Mean	Gberika	Rochain	Rochint	Mean
ROK17	2.2	1.9	2.1	2.1	2.9	2.4	2.4	2.5
ROK18	2.0	2.8	2.3	2.4	2.8	2.8	2.3	2.4
ROK19	2.8	2.3	2.0	2.2	2.4	2.0	2.3	2.2
ROK20	2.4	2.1	2.3	2.3	2.7	2.2	2.4	2.3
ROK16 (check)	1.8	1.6	1.8	1.7	1.5	1.3	1.7	1.5
CV (%)	12.2	14.6	18.2	15	19.7	22.9	14.4	19
LSD (0.05)	8.2	8.2	8.2	8.2	8.2	8.1	8.2	8.2
Soil	Sandy loam	Loam	Gravelly clay loam		Clay loam	Sandy loam	Loam	
pH (water)	5.0	4.9	5.1		5.5	4.8	5.0	
CEC (meq/100g)	11.4	10.2	13.2		15.1	9.9	11.1	
Organic C (%)	1.2	0.9	1.4		2.1	0.8	1.8	
Total rainfall (mm)	2,156				2,256			

and South Sierra Leone. ROK17 is preferred by North Sierra Leone farmers because it is awnless, which makes threshing with the feet less painful. It also has better cooking and eating qualities.

ROK18, ROK19, and ROK20 are short-duration varieties superior to ROK16 in plant type, disease resistance, and phenotypic acceptability. They are recommended for the low rainfall areas of the north. Grain size ranges from slender to medium bold, as preferred by northern farmers. □

Integrated germplasm improvement—irrigated

ASD18, a blast (Bl)-resistant rice variety for Tamil Nadu

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Bl-resistant, short-duration, medium-slender rice culture AS34011, selected from the cross ADT31/IR50, was released as ASD18 by the Tamil Nadu G.D. Naidu Agricultural University in Jan 1991. It is recommended as an alternative to IR50 and TKM9 for summer (Mar-Jun), first season (Jun-Sep), and second season (Nov-Feb) planting.

ASD18 is 90 cm tall with 105-110 d growth duration. Mean grain yield was 7.3 t/ha over 6 yr at RRS, 5.7 t/ha in multilocation trials over 2 yr at seven research stations throughout Tamil Nadu, and 5.9 t/ha under Adaptive Research Trials (ART) in 52 farmers' fields. Total dry mass was 18.2 t/ha (8.5 t grain and 9.7 t straw) at Ambasamudram; potential grain yield was 10.1 t/ha under ART.

It is resistant to Bl and moderately resistant to sheath rot and tungro (Table 1). It is resistant to brown planthopper and stem borer and moderately resistant to gall midge and leafhopper (Table 2). □

Table 1. Reaction of ASD18 to major diseases in Tamil Nadu, India.

Variety	Reaction ^a						
	Blast			Sheath rot ASD-N	Sheath blight ASD-A	RTV	
	ADT-A	DBE-A	ASD-N			ADT-A	CBE-A
ASD18	1	3	3	5	7	4	5
IR50	3	9	9	7	9	5	3
TKM9	3	7	7	7	9	8	9

^aBy the Standard evaluation system for rice (SES) scale. N = natural condition, A = artificial condition, ADT = Aduthurai, ASD = Ambasamudram, CBE = Coimbatore.

Table 2. Reaction of ASD18 to major pests in Tamil Nadu, India.

Variety	Reaction ^a						
	BPH		SB		GM	LF	
	ADT-A	ASD-A	ASD-N	MDU-A	MDU-A	CBE-N	ASD-A
ASD18	3	5	3	0	5	7	5
IR50	9	5	3		3	9	7
TKM9	9	9	3		0	9	7

^aBY SES. BPH = brown planthopper, SB = stem borer, GM = gall midge, LF = leafhopper. ADT = Aduthurai, ASD = Ambasamudram. MDU = Madurai, CBE = Coimbatore. N = natural condition, A = artificial condition, (-) = not tested.

Integrated germplasm improvement—rainfed lowland

Three new varieties of short-duration rice released in Cambodia

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Short-duration rices (120 d or less) cover almost 25% of Cambodia's rice area. In the dry season, they are grown in about 10% of the area, either irrigated or with receding water. In the wet season, they are grown in about 15% of the area as a rainfed lowland crop.

A number of traditional early varieties